

Traffic light management system using image processing

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Submitted: October 1, 2013

Accepted: November 10, 2013

ABSTRACT

Traffic control is important. Traffic congestion creates many problems in our everyday lives. Travel time increases which lead to waste of time and fuel. A system that can manage traffic through the efficient use of traffic lights by applying an algorithm to control the time for the signals of a traffic light would be beneficial. A system was developed by using a modified waterfall model. Data from the City Traffic Operations Management (CITOM) were utilized. Images were taken using a digital camera from the GMT building and the Montesclaros Building to acquire snapshots of actual traffic zones. An image processing module was developed after reading on image processing and edge detection. A traffic density module was created to determine the density for each phase. A traffic management module was created by taking the phase densities into consideration. In the system, the snapshots were analyzed. After analysis, the system applied an algorithm which adjusts the time of a certain intersection based from its density. The system also stores analyzed data into a database. CITOM personnel gave the system an overall rating of 4.260 on a 5-point rating system, which is interpreted as completely acceptable. Meanwhile, motorists rated the system's importance, and 100% of them wanted it to be implemented.

Keywords: *traffic light management system, image processing, traffic density*

I. INTRODUCTION

The number of vehicles around the world is increasing (Al-Alawi, 2009). The growth of modern cities along with their heavy reliance on cars as their primary mode of transportation signified that traffic control is now more important. Travel time to and from work is time wasted. Traffic delays would impinge on productivity. Traffic is linked with road accidents (Robinson-Mosher & Egner, 2009). The country

has experienced growth in the number of vehicles over the period of 2002-2009 from four million vehicles in 2002 to six million vehicles in 2009 (National Statistics Coordination Board, 2010). Cebu also has its number of vehicles growing (Vergel, 2007). For the period of 2000-2006, there has been an average of 4% annual growth in number of vehicles. Cebu is the province that has the most number of vehicles registered in 2005 at 266,086 (National Statistics Coordination Board,

2006). There is a confirmed growing trend in the number of vehicles registered in Cebu City.

City Traffic Operations Management, or CITOM, stated that underground traffic detectors cost 50,000 Philippine pesos each for replacement. There are three broken detectors in the P. Del Rosario-Pelaez intersection and another three broken detectors in the P. Del Rosario-Junquera intersection (City Traffic Operations Management).

II. THE STUDY

This study aimed to develop a traffic light management system using image processing.

Particularly, this study intended to: (1) create a model of the intersections under the study; (2) model the existing traffic system; (3) develop an image analyzer based on traffic density; (4) store traffic density information per phase; and (5) test and evaluate the developed system.

Two intersections—P. Del Rosario-Pelaez and P. Del Rosario-Junquera, were modeled. The system is to be used under heavy traffic congestion situations. The proposed system is not designed to replace traffic enforcers, but to support them in their decisions for traffic management.

Stakeholders identified were: (1) motorists; (2) the City Traffic Operations Management; and (3) the academe. Included under motorists would be commuters, public and private vehicle drivers. The administration of the City Traffic Operations Management would benefit from the system. The academe would include researchers and students who are interested in the topic.

Cebu City motorists. Reclaiming time lost due to traffic would improve lives of many commuters (Robinson-Mosher & Egner, 2009). Less congestion would mean that there would be fewer accidents, saving lives. Goods and services can be transported faster to their clients.

City Traffic Operations Management. Traditional fixed time control schemes can waste time when there are lanes with heavier traffic (Robinson-Mosher & Egner, 2009). This should extend to situations where some lanes are empty

while the others are not, yet they are stopped by the signal light.

An effective traffic management system will give more time to lanes which have more traffic and less time to lanes that are empty. Such a system should prevent deadlocks. A deadlock means that resources (i.e., road space) are non-sharable, motorists waiting for resources to be available while also holding resources, resources allocated not capable of being preempted, and motorists waiting for resources from each other (Coffman, Elphick & Shoshani, 1971).

Academe. This research will attempt to combine the advantages of Canny and Sobel edge detection algorithms to create a modified edge detection algorithm. The algorithm dubbed as traffic light management system using image processing to detect traffic density can be used for further researches. As a result, additional knowledge would be created.

Definition of Terms

Signal group is the basic unit of a traffic control scheme. It is the collection of lights that always show the same color. A signal group corresponds to a single movement on the intersection (Van Kitwijk, 2008).

Phase is a set of signal groups that can proceed concurrently without conflicts between major movements. Some movements are allowed, however, even if they cause conflicts such as allowing pedestrians to cross the street while right-turn movements are occurring (Van Kitwijk, 2008).

Cycle is an iteration of a set of phases during the course of traffic management. One example would be the iteration between phases of P. Del Rosario and Pelaez.

Traffic light management is the manipulation of the flow of vehicles by timing the signals from traffic lights.

Image processing is a form of signal processing where the input is an image and the output is either an image or a set of characteristics or parameters related to the image.

Edge detection is a fundamental tool in

image processing that aims to identify points in a digital image at which image brightness has discontinuities.

Traffic density is the measure of the heaviness of vehicle flow in a road. For this study, it is measured by the amount of area occupied by vehicles.

Literature Review

The traffic light management system using image processing is composed of three elements: (1) the traffic light system; (2) image processing; and (3) traffic density detection.

The software engineering paradigm used is a modified waterfall model where phases can overlap when needed (Munassar & Govardhan, 2010). The modified waterfall model allows it to be more flexible than a pure waterfall model where backtracking is not allowed. Implementation of easy parts does not need to come after hard ones.

An image processing tool for vehicle detection was developed which used edge based technique that is less sensitive to noise (Siyal & Fathy, 1995). The threshold selection is done dynamically to compensate the effects of variations of lighting and it does not impose any significant computational cost. This allows image processing in differently lighted areas.

Image processing techniques were combined to achieve a better analysis of the images (Martin & Tosunoglu, 1997). Some techniques such as the Edge Detection Techniques, Grey-Level Segmentation Techniques, Iterative Method and Digital Morphology were used to minimize computation time.

Edge detection significantly reduces the amount of data and filters out useless information while preserving important structural properties in the image. Two edge detection algorithms were explained: Sobel and Canny (Green, 2002a,b)

Traffic density detection, over the years, has been an important study. Its use ranges from traffic light management to analysis of congestion (Li, Han, Lee & Gonzales, 2007).

The modern traffic lights have been used since 1920 (Crandall, 2007). Traffic light systems

have evolved into smart traffic management system being able to make decision based from communication.

There are also other vehicle detectors such as loop, radar, infrared, ultrasonic, and microwave detectors. These sensors are expensive with limited capacity and involve installation, maintenance, and implementation difficulties. For example, loop sensor might need maintenance due to road ground deformation or metal barriers near the road that prevents effective detection using radar sensors. In recent years, video processing techniques have attracted researchers for vehicle detection (Ozkurt & Camci, 2009).

Furthermore, video image processing was also used to calculate the density of traffic by counting the number of vehicles. The system has some limitations such as visual homogeneity requirement and its effectiveness depends on the speed of moving objects (Ozkurt & Camci, 2009).

There are four conditions that are necessary for a traffic deadlock (Coffman, Elphick & Shoshani, 1971). These are: (1) mutual exclusion condition where the resources are non-sharable; (2) hold-and-wait condition where processes are holding resources while requesting for additional resources; (3) the no-preemptive condition where resources held by processes cannot be preempted; and (4) the circular wait condition where processes in the system form a circular list (each process in the list is waiting for a resource held by the next process).

A web-based intelligent traffic management system was created (Al-Alawi, 2009). This system links together the nodes, or traffic lights at various intersections. This allows the nodes to communicate with each other rather than operating independently.

Fixed-time schemes require the duration and order of green phases to be fixed. Fixed-time schemes use historical data to predict traffic situations. However, as fixed-time schemes are based on historical data, they cannot adapt to real-time situations.

Traffic-actuated control schemes require

detectors to acquire information about the current situation. The decision to terminate the green phase requires knowledge that the last vehicle of the queue that has built up at the stop of the red phase has passed.

Under traffic-adaptive control, the entire intersection is taken into account in order to decide whether to continue the current green phase or to switch to a different phase. This is different compared to traffic-actuated control that uses only the presence of demand on the active green phase to extend or to switch phases (Van Kitwijk, 2008).

CITOM stated that due to broken traffic detectors, a fixed-plan system is used to direct traffic. The cycle time, or time an entire cycle consisting of phases takes to complete, is 200 seconds in this case. In the intersections under the study, there are only two phases in each intersection. For the P. Del Rosario-Pelaez intersection, one phase is the P. Del Rosario phase where traffic along P. Del Rosario travels straight in both directions. The other phase is the Pelaez phase where traffic goes straight, turns left and right. For the P. Del Rosario-Junquera intersection, one phase is the P. Del Rosario phase where traffic travels straight in both directions. The other phase is the Junquera phase where traffic goes straight, turns left and right. For these phases, the P. Del Rosario phase has 130 seconds while the Pelaez and the Junquera phases have 70 seconds each (City Traffic Operations Management).

Section 9(b) of Article II of Chapter II of Republic Act 4136 states that no motor vehicle should exceed 2.5 meters in width. Only one vehicle may occupy the width of a lane (City Traffic Operations Management, personal communication).

Theoretical Framework

The Sobel edge detection algorithm performs a 2D spatial gradient measurement on an image (Green, 2002b). It uses a pair of 3x3 convolution masks, one to estimate between columns and the other to estimate between rows.

The Canny Edge Detection Algorithm performs a series of steps, starting with a Gaussian filter (Green, 2002a). The Gaussian Filter removes noise in the original image. The edge strength is determined by taking the: (1) gradient of the image; (2) edge direction (inverse tangent of the y-gradient over the x-gradient). A y-gradient of zero means a zero angle while having both y-gradient and x-gradient equal to zero means that the angle is 90 degrees. The next step is to classify the directions into one of four categories. If the angle falls between 0 and 22.5 degrees or between 157.5 and 180 degrees, it falls into category 1. If it falls between 22.5 and 67.5 degrees, it falls into category 2. Category 3 contains angles between 67.5 and 112.5 degrees. Category 4 contains angles between 112.5 and 157.5 degrees. The next step is non-maximum suppression where pixels are set to 0 if they are not part of edges, resulting in a thin line. An added step for the Canny Edge Detection is Hysteresis, which eliminates streaking (or breaking up of an edge contour) by using two thresholds: a high threshold and a low threshold (instead of simply one). A pixel higher than the low threshold is marked as an edge pixel, and pixels that are connected and have a value greater than the high threshold are marked as edge pixels.

Fixed-time schemes require the duration and order of green phases to be fixed. However, fixed-time control schemes may be replaced using a clock as traffic situation changes over time. The assumption behind the fixed-time schemes is that traffic patterns can be accurately predicted based on historical data. However, as fixed-time schemes are based on historical data, they cannot adapt to real-time situations (Van Kitwijk, 2008).

Video image processing was used to detect the number of vehicles by detecting the number of moving objects (Ozkurt & Camci, 2009). However, they faced limitations such as visual homogeneity requirements. Their algorithm was also very dependent on the speeds of moving objects to determine the number of vehicles.

A snapshot approach was opted as visual homogeneity does not matter when looking for traffic density. Traffic density in this approach is calculated by the ratio of the area occupied by cars (predetermined area to the total area). Data were processed to produce the density of traffic per lane. This information were used in the overall analysis of the current traffic surrounding the intersections.

Canny and Sobel Edge Detection algorithms were chosen for the study. Canny edge detection can reduce unnecessary features from the input image while Sobel Edge Detection determines thick edges.

A system design of the proposed system is created, as shown below:

Figure 1. System Design

Images were then fed into the Canny-Sobel Edge Detection. The processed images were fed to the traffic density analyzer, where the traffic density were calculated per lane. Alternatively, each lane's density was provided directly without using images. After each lane's density was calculated, the traffic density for each phase was calculated by dividing the sum of each lane's density with the number of lanes in the associated phase. The density of each phase was determined,

and this information was used to compute the amount of time. This was used in the phase time adjustment should the adaptive scheme be chosen. The time for each phase at each intersection was adjusted based on the information from the traffic density analyzer. After processing the image through the traffic density analyzer, the date, time, location, and density were stored in the database.

Figure 2. Lane Traffic Density Processing

Figure 2 shows the Lane Traffic Density Processing Sub-Module. This sub-module works by extracting each lane by using pre-defined polygons. Each lane was processed by searching for the first white pixel from the left and the first white pixel from the right and making every pixel in between as a white pixel. The number of white pixels was calculated and divided over the total amount of space in the lane's polygon to determine the lane's traffic density.

Figure 3. Traffic Density Synthesizer

Figure 3 shows the Traffic Density Synthesizer Sub-Module. This sub-module works by adding together the densities of all the lanes of the phase. The phase density was then determined by dividing the total of the lane densities by the number of lanes in the phase.

III. METHODOLOGY

The software engineering paradigm used was a modified waterfall model where phases

were allowed to overlap when needed (Munassar & Govardhan, 2010). The phases for this project were data gathering, design and coding, testing, and evaluation.

Figure 4. Modified Waterfall Model

Data Gathering

Data gathering was performed by conducting an interview with CITOM to learn about the traffic situation in the intersections. The maximum cycle time, the different phases at each intersection and the amount of time given for each phase were gathered. The lengths of roads were gathered from the Cebu City Geographic Information System Center. Library research and literature review were conducted to learn more regarding image processing.

Snapshots of the intersections were taken from the GMT Building and the Montesclaros Building as vantage points for the P. Del Rosario-Junquera intersection and the P. Del Rosario-Pelaez intersection, respectively.

Design and Coding

The system was then designed with the creation of three modules. An image processing module used edge detection to determine the objects in the image. A traffic density module used the processed images to determine the amount of space occupied by vehicles. A traffic management module then adjusted time given for each phase using the results of the traffic density module. A database was also designed to store the data from the traffic density module

The image processing module was created by

benchmarking Canny, Sobel, Homogeneity, and Difference edge detection algorithms. Choosing from the edge detection algorithms would follow.

The traffic density module was created by analyzing the processed images and calculating the area that was occupied by vehicles per lane. The average lane density of each phase would be used to determine the amount of time for each phase.

The traffic management module was created from the data gathered from CITOM and the Cebu City Geographic Information System Center. From the gathered data, an algorithm was created by taking into consideration the cycle time as well as the phase times calculated from average lane density.

The database was designed to store the date, the time, the location, and the density of an image that was processed by the traffic density module.

Testing

Individual module testing, module integration testing, and system testing were conducted. Individual modules were tested to check correct performance. Module integration was tested to see if the modules interacted correctly. System testing was conducted to check overall system performance.

Evaluation

The system was then evaluated by CITOM technical personnel as well as motorists. A survey was conducted among CITOM technical personnel to test the system processes, and another survey was conducted among motorists to test the system goals. The CITOM evaluation instrument was created by using a 5-point scale where 1 is Not Acceptable, 2 is Slightly Acceptable, 3 is Moderately Acceptable, 4 is Very Acceptable, and 5 is Completely Acceptable, based on Henning's scale (Henning, 2009). The scale is akin to saying that 1 is poor, 2 is Fair, 3 is Good, 4 is Very Good, and 5 is Excellent. The motorist evaluation instrument was created by using a Yes/No scale. The questionnaires for the evaluation stage for both the motorists and CITOM personnel were constructed based on the readings and observations of the traffic situations in Cebu City. Specific items were formulated with the

aim of evaluating the importance of the system developed. These instruments were pretested to detect their clarity and unambiguity to the intended respondents.

The CITOM technical personnel were sampled purposively. A computer programmer from the Traffic Control Group, a planning officer, and an engineer from the Planning Department were sampled. Their survey involved rating the system based on functionality and usability. Their comments and suggestions were also taken. The survey results were averaged and interpreted, where 1.00 to 1.80 means Not Acceptable, 1.81 to 2.60 means Slightly Acceptable, 2.61 to 3.40 means Moderately Acceptable, 3.41 to 4.20 means Very Acceptable, and 4.21 to 5.00 means Completely Acceptable.

There were 30 motorists surveyed through convenience sampling. A sample size of 30 qualified as a large sample. They were asked regarding the acceptability of the project, and their responses were tallied. The results of the surveys were collected and summarized using their mean score (Jaisingh, 2006).

IV. ALGORITHM

The image processing module utilized both Canny and Sobel Edge Detection Methods in creating the Canny-Sobel Edge Detection.

Figure 5. Applying Edge Detection

Figure 5(a) shows a road before being processed. Figure 5(b) shows the road after being processed with Canny Edge Detection. Figure 5(c) shows the road after being processed with Sobel Edge Detection. Figure 5(d) shows the road after being processed with the Canny-Sobel Edge Detection. Canny Edge Detection was applied then Sobel Edge Detection was applied to achieve the Canny-Sobel Processed Image.

Figure 6. Density Calculation

In figure 6(a) a copy of the selected image was made. In figure 6(b) Canny-Sobel Edge Detection was applied. In figure 6(c) a red background image was prepared. A predefined polygon model was used to crop the road from the image. In figure 6(d) the polygon model was pasted onto the red background. The image was cropped in the maximum width and height of the polygon model, giving a rectangle. The images of the roads were often not parallel with the vertical. There were irrelevant data in the cropped image due to roads not always forming a rectangle. In figure 6(e) the road were colored black and the edges with white. The area occupied by the cars was calculated by scanning pixel by pixel per row from the left until a white pixel was reached. If a white pixel was found, a white pixel was searched from the right this time. Once a white pixel was found from the right, all pixels between the two white pixels were converted to white. This process was repeated until all rows in the image had been scanned. The area of white pixels was divided over the entire area excluding the red portions. To determine the

traffic density.

After the traffic density were taken, the information were stored in the database together with the date, time and location.

A model of the intersections was created by using information regarding their phases.

In CITOM's fixed-plan system, the cycle time is 200 seconds. The time allotted for P. Del Rosario is 130 seconds while Pelaez and Junquera are allotted 70 seconds each. As a result, weights were assigned to each phase by getting the ratio of the time allotted for the phases. P. Del Rosario phase received a weight of 13 while Pelaez and Junquera phases received a weight of 7 each.

The formula for time per phase is as follows:

$$t_n = \frac{p_{w_n}}{\sum p_w} * t_{max}$$

$$p_{w_n} = \frac{(l_n * w_n)}{\sum w}$$

Where:

t_n – Time for phase n in the intersection

t_{max} – Maximum time (240 seconds)

p_{w_n} – Weighted percentage of phase n

w_n – Weight of phase n

l – Average lane density of the phase

$\sum w$ – Sum of weights of the phases in the intersection

$\sum p_w$ – Sum of weighted percentages in the intersection

IV. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

System Testing

System testing was conducted to check any possible bugs and its performance as a whole.

Table 1 shows that loading maps as well as background pictures did not show any problems. Various user errors regarding the background image zoom level, render grid, signal cycle time, timeline zoom, cars per hour, simulation speed, and simulation steps were automatically corrected.

Table 1. System Testing Results

Case Scenario	Expected outcome	Actual Outcome	Pass / Fail
Load another map	Map loads	Map loads with limited functionalities	Pass
Load our map	Load map with all functionalities	Map loads with all functionalities	Pass
Load Background Picture	Load picture	Picture loads	Pass
Background image zoom > 400	Auto adjust to 400	The spin edit will have a value of 400	Pass
Background image zoom < 0	Auto adjust to 1	The spin edit will have a value of 1	Pass
Render grid to > 100	Auto adjust to 100	The spin edit will have a value of 100	Pass
Render grid to < 1	Auto adjust to 1	The spin edit will have a value of 1	Pass
Signal Cycle time to > 240	Auto adjust to 240	The spin edit will have a value of 240	Pass
Signal Cycle time to < 10	Auto adjust to 10	The spin edit will have a value of 10	Pass
Timeline zoom to > 20	Auto adjust to 20	The spin edit will have a value of 20	Pass
Timeline zoom to < 1	Auto adjust to 1	The spin edit will have a value of 1	Pass
Cars/hr to > 100,000	Auto adjust to 100,000	The spin edit will have a value of 100,000	Pass
Simulation Speed to > 10	Auto adjust to 10	The spin edit will have a value of 10	Pass
Simulation Speed to < 1	Auto adjust to 1	The spin edit will have a value of 1	Pass
Sim steps to > 30	Auto adjust to 30	The spin edit will have a value of 30	Pass
Sim steps to < 1	Auto adjust to 1	The spin edit will have a value of 1	Pass

Motorist Survey Results

Table 2. Motorist Survey

Question	No	%	Yes	%
Are you aware that there are underground detectors that help manage traffic?	9	30	21	70
Are you aware that some of these detectors are broken?	16	53.3	14	46.7
Do you think that these broken detectors present a problem with traffic management?	1	3.3	29	96.7
Do you think that our proposed system is a solution to the broken detectors?	0	0	30	100
Do you think that the proposed system is necessary to alleviate traffic congestion?	1	3.3	29	96.7
Do you think that the proposed system is beneficial to motorists like you?	0	0	30	100
Do you think that the proposed system is practical or feasible to use?	2	6.7	28	93.3
Would you like to have such a system implemented?	0	0	30	100

According to surveys conducted for the motorists, 30% of them were not aware that there were underground detectors that helped manage traffic. Out of those who knew that there were underground detectors, 33% of them were not

aware that some of the detectors were broken. As a whole, 53.3% of the motorists surveyed revealed that they were not aware that there were broken traffic detectors. Also, 96.7% of those surveyed thought that these broken detectors presented a problem with traffic management.

100% of motorists surveyed agreed that the proposed system is a solution to the broken detectors and that such a system is beneficial. Also, they like to have such a system implemented. An insignificant percentage (3.3% and 6.7%, respectively) of motorists interviewed said that the system is unnecessary and impractical.

Figure 7. Motorist Survey

CITOM SURVEY RESULTS

Table 3. CITOM Survey Interpretation

Rating	Interpretation
1.00-1.80	Not Acceptable
1.81-2.60	Slightly Acceptable
2.61-3.40	Moderately Acceptable
3.41-4.20	Very Acceptable
4.21-5.00	Completely Acceptable

The CITOM surveys used a 5-point rating system, where 5 is the highest possible rating. A mean rating of 1.00 to 1.80 is interpreted as not acceptable. A mean rating of 1.81 to 2.60 is interpreted as slightly acceptable. A mean rating of 2.61 to 3.40 is interpreted as moderately acceptable. A mean rating of 3.41 to 4.20 is interpreted as very acceptable. A mean rating of 4.21 to 5.00 is interpreted as completely acceptable.

Table 4. CITOM Survey: Functionality

Question	Raw Score	Mean Score	Acceptability
The system models the intersections of P. Del Rosario-Pelaez and P. Del Rosario-Junquera	14	4.7	Completely Acceptable
The image analysis module creates an accurate analysis of the image	13	4.3	Completely Acceptable
The traffic density module creates an accurate report of the traffic density	13	4.3	Completely Acceptable
The simulation models the fixed-time plan accurately	13	4.3	Completely Acceptable
The simulation models the proposed solution effectively	13	4.3	Completely Acceptable

According to surveys with the CITOM technical personnel, functionality had a mean rating of 4.4. This is interpreted as completely acceptable. The system’s model of the intersections of P. Del Rosario-Pelaez and P. Del Rosario-Junquera had a mean rating of 4.7, which is interpreted as completely acceptable. The image analysis module was given a mean rating of 4.3, which is interpreted as completely acceptable. The traffic density module was given a mean rating of 4.3, which is interpreted as completely acceptable. The system’s model of the fixed-time plan was given a mean rating of 4.3, which is interpreted as completely acceptable. The system’s proposed solution had a mean rating of 4.3, which is interpreted as completely acceptable.

Figure 8. CITOM Survey: Functionality

Table 5. CITOM Survey: Usability

Question	Raw Score	Mean Score	Acceptability
The simulation has a display that is easy to understand	12	4	Very Acceptable
The system provides instructions for use	11	3.7	Very Acceptable
All system components are working properly	13	4.3	Completely Acceptable
The system does not slow down during simulation	13	4.3	Completely Acceptable

Usability had a mean rating of 4.075. The system’s display’s ease of understanding was rated 4, which is interpreted as very acceptable. The system’s instructions for use were rated 3.7, which is interpreted as very acceptable. The system components were rated 4.3, which is interpreted as completely acceptable. The system’s performance is also rated 4.3, which is interpreted as completely acceptable.

Figure 9. CITOM Survey: Usability

Overall, the system had a mean rating of 4.260, which is interpreted as completely acceptable.

Summary

Traffic congestion creates a waste of fuel. Managing traffic congestion would be beneficial. A traffic management system was developed by using a modified waterfall model. Data were

gathered from CITOM as well as the GMT and Montesclaros buildings. The image pre-processor, traffic density analyzer, and traffic management simulator modules were developed. The system was evaluated by CITOM personnel and motorists with high ratings.

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The P. Del Rosario-Pelaez and P. Del Rosario-Junquera intersections were successfully modeled. The phases were modeled to create the traffic flow situation. The existing traffic system was modeled successfully. The fixed-time system used by the intersections due to broken detectors was modeled. The image analyzer based on traffic density was developed. Traffic density were determined after analyzing the image. The traffic density information per phase was stored in a database which contained the date, time, location, and density of the various processed images. The system was tested and evaluated by CITOM personnel and motorists.

The system is to be implemented from the surveys conducted with the motorists and CITOM personnel. The user interface will improve if it will be tested in a larger scale. Further studies shall be conducted to systems that will enhance traffic light time management and aid in the decision for road modifications.

For implementation, an overhead camera must be used. High-end infrastructure will speed up image analysis. Lower image resolution will speed up analysis. Having more image snapshots for traffic density calculation per cycle will give a better management rather than one snapshot per cycle.

Originality Index:	92 %
Similarity Index:	8 %
Paper ID:	384599913
Grammarly:	Checked

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